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Canada's Experience in Monetary Appraisal of Archival Documents: Characteristics of Research Sources and Basic Concepts

Objective. The paper aims to identify the main sources of information on the monetary appraisal of archival documents and to analyse the main conceptual principles underlying this process. **Methods.** The following methods were used in the course of the research: historical source analysis, historical comparison, and conceptual analysis.

Results. The authors characterised the main sources of information on the valuation of archival documents, in particular, the websites of the National Archival Appraisal Board, Library and Archives of Canada, the Canadian Cultural Property Export Review Board, the Antiquarian Booksellers' Association of America, proceedings of the 2007 conference in Ottawa "The Future of Monetary Valuation in Canada", and forum reports (2022) on the topic "Much More Than Money". The main conceptual principles used by archivists and other experts in determining the monetary value of documents are identified. **Conclusions.** The sources of information on the appraisal of archival artefacts in Canada are quite representative and provide an overall picture of the organisation of these processes and the results of their implementation. The criteria for the appraisal of archival documents can be applied to the valuation and purchase of library collections and individual book artefacts. Despite differences in the organisation of the appraisal process, the conceptual approaches to the process itself in Canada and Ukraine are almost identical. However, the experience of Canadian archivists is valuable and requires in-depth study, especially in the areas of monetary valuation of audiovisual documents and documents in electronic form.

Keywords: monetary appraisal; archival documents; concepts; research sources; archives; libraries; Canada

Introduction

The Operational Action Plan for the implementation of the Strategy for the Protection of Documentary Heritage as a Guarantee of National Identity and Statehood for the period 2025–2027 states: "developing and submitting to the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine a draft resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on improving the methodology for the monetary appraisal of documents in the National Archival Fund" (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2025). In this regard, it is relevant to study the experience of different countries in organising the monetary appraisal of archival documents. It should be noted that foreign archival science theorists, such as H. Jenkinson, T. Schellenberg, V. Avtokratov, and C. Kecskemeti, have generally ignored this issue. Unfortunately, such experience is lacking in both European and global archival science in general. The only positive example at present is the practice of Canadian archivists, antique dealers, booksellers, and auctioneers in valuing archival artefacts, although in Canada itself it has not yet become the subject of historiographical research. First of all, it is necessary to identify a group of information sources that raise the issue of monetary appraisal of archival documents, as well as the basic conceptual principles for resolving it. The criteria for evaluating archival documents (level of significance, collection value, presence of rare illustrations and decorations, state of preservation, etc.) can be extrapolated to the practice of the antiquarian book trade. These issues have not been examined in Ukraine, nor has any historiographical analysis of these problems been carried out in Canada.

Methods

The *objective* of this article is to identify the main sources of information on the monetary appraisal of archival documents and to analyse the main conceptual foundations of this process. The *methods* used in this study are historical source analysis, historical comparative analysis, and conceptual analysis. Thanks to historical source analysis, the main sources of information in the history of the organisation of monetary appraisal of archival artefacts in Canada were identified. Historical comparative analysis helped to find similarities and differences in the conceptual foundations for determining the monetary value of archival documents in Canada and Ukraine. The conceptual method made it possible to specify and understand concepts that are not used in our country when determining the monetary value of archival sources (for example, “fair price of documents”, “sentimental value of documents”, “intangible value of documents”, “tax deductions”, etc.). Comparative analysis contributed to the understanding of Canadian conceptual methods for determining the price of audiovisual and electronic documents, which are innovative for Ukraine. However, this experience requires further detailed research.

Results and Discussion

The sources of information on the Canadian experience of monetary appraisal of archival documents are diverse in composition, nature and informational significance and are of research interest. We will focus on the most representative ones, presented in the works of the most famous Canadian researchers, published in archival periodicals, in particular the journal of the Association of Canadian Archivists “Archivaria” and on the websites of those Canadian institutions whose interests and practical activities relate to the monetary appraisal of archival documents.

Operational and retrospective information on the procedures and methods of appraising archival documents can be found on the websites of the National Archival Appraisal Board / Conseil National d'Évaluation des Archives (NAAB/CNÉA – hereinafter we provide the abbreviations of this and other organisations in the French version – CNÉA), Library and Archives Canada / Bibliothèque et Archives Canada (LAC/BAC – hereinafter referred to as BAC), the Canadian Cultural Property Export Review Board / Commission canadienne d'examen des exportations de biens culturels (CCPERB/ CCEEBC – hereinafter referred to as CCEEBC).

The CNÉA website contains publications of its evaluation committees' reports, which are valuable sources of information and reference for both experts and researchers in the theory and methodology of monetary appraisal. The opportunity for expert appraisers to familiarise themselves with CNÉA reports on the appraisal of archival documents can strengthen appraisal methodology and contribute to reliable and objective justification of their value.

The CNÉA website features the Newsletter of the National Archival Appraisal Board / Bulletin du Conseil national d'évaluation des archives (6 volumes, 10 issues for 2019–2024), which covers a wide range of issues related to the monetary appraisal of archival documents. The articles, reports and news items of the Board's committees (Monetary Appraisal Review Committee, Ad Hoc Committee on the Monetary Appraisal of Electronic Records, Research Committee) contain information on the Board's strategies, standards, policies and implementation tools for monetary appraisal; the “changing context of monetary appraisal” and trends in these documents with sales price tables (Évaluation, 2019, 2020); the history of practices, principles, methods, criteria and models of valuation; legal aspects of determining the value of cultural property; interpretation of “fair market value”; features of assessing electronic documents; instructions for writing monetary appraisal reports; use of valuation databases for comparison; conducting webinars, online workshops, and master classes on various topics related to monetary appraisal (master classes launched in 2019); discussion of monetary appraisal manuals.

The state and prospects of the theory, methodology and practice of monetary appraisal of archival documents are presented in the materials of the CNÉA scientific forums. The first such gathering was a conference in Lac Beauport, Quebec, in 1976, attended by representatives from Canada, the United States and the United Kingdom, which demonstrated international interest in this issue. The conference addressed issues of policy, procedures, legislation on appraisal and tax credits, and appraisal principles and techniques.

The most ambitious of all CNÉA forums was the 2007 conference in Ottawa, “The Future of Monetary Appraisal in Canada” (“L’avenir de l’évaluation monétaire au Canada”). The conference report, conceptual sessions containing materials from discussions between representatives with significant experience in appraisal and archiving (Marcel Caillat, Patricia Kennedy, Brock Silversides, Sonia Lismer, Stephen Lunsford, and others) is an important source for studying the strategy, policy, legal basis, organisation, and methodology of conducting expert examinations and monetary appraisal of all types of archival documents, including electronic and microfilms. Separate sessions of the conference were devoted to the methodology of appraising archival documents and the consequences of their monetary appraisal in a hypothetical and theoretical context (Laplante, 2007). The analysis of the contexts of creation and acquisition of various types of documents – political archives, architectural documentation, audiovisual documents – was valuable for expert appraisal, as were the identification of elements that may influence appraisal and the emphasis on the importance of sound appraisal. The emergence and spread of new types of documents in digital format stimulated a review of traditional valuation methods. The monetary appraisal of digital archival documents was considered by conference participants in the context of the valuation of other monuments based on traditional archival valuation criteria. The conference presented the views of auctioneers, booksellers, archivists, librarians, representatives of the Canada Revenue Agency / Agence du revenu du Canada (CRA/ARC – hereinafter referred to as ARC), university professors on monetary appraisal and its specifics for different types of documents, in particular audiovisual and electronic documents. Agence du revenu du Canada (CRA/ARC – hereinafter ARC), and university professors on monetary appraisal and its specifics for different types of documents, in particular audiovisual and electronic documents.

At the 2022 Forum (2022), dedicated to the theme “Much more than money” (“Bien plus que de l’argent”), there were discussed the issues strategies and prospects for the monetary appraisal of documentary heritage donations, the nature of the specialised market for archival documents, factors influencing the reliability of valuation, the development of standards for professional practice in the monetary appraisal of various types of documents (graphic, cartographic, architectural, audiovisual), the definition of criteria for a reasoned justification of the value of objects being appraised and the determination of “fair market value”, methods for finding sources of market data to justify the proposed price, current trends and changes in the manuscript market, sales precedents and their application, and approaches to the appraisal of digital records. As we can see, CNÉA forums provide an opportunity to assess trends in research on the monetary appraisal of archival documents.

A wide range of issues, namely: instructions on the mandatory information to be provided by appraisers, recommendations on the template for determining the monetary value, parameters for describing the object origin, certificate of authenticity, state of preservation, history of exhibitions and publications, declaration of alienation or act of transfer, report on archival appraisal and description, reference to the purchase price, changes in the estimated value on the date of alienation, justification of exceptional interest, with the addition of digital photographs of objects) and a request for certification and models to be used in the monetary appraisal of archival

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documents are discussed in the Monetary Appraisal Guide developed by the CCEEBC (*Guide pour les Évaluations Monétaires*, 2024).

The appraisal methodologies, which included research into the market for archival goods and identification of the best ones, analysis of market data, comparison of market sales and previous valuations, reasoned justification of prices, identification of factors to be taken into account for best practices in the appraisal of archival cultural assets, principles of sampling and segmentation in monetary appraisal, characteristics of monetary appraisal of funds or individual archival documents, requirements for monetary appraisal report forms are presented in the 2020 CCEEBC Strategy for the Appraisal of Archival Cultural Assets, which is a supplement to the Monetary Appraisal Guide (*Stratégies pour L'évaluation*, 2020).

Sources of information on appraisal results have become widespread on the Internet, especially on the websites of sellers operating in the field of online sales of archival documents. The use of online resources prevails over the use of traditional printed sources, such as catalogues or sales reports. However, as Canadian experts warn, this information should be used with caution, and it is better to refer to reputable dealers who distribute online catalogues, including auction catalogues. In addition, information about prices for documents on Internet resources is inferior to that for printed books, which is explained by the lower activity of the market for archival artefacts and, sometimes, the confidentiality of information about document sales. It is possible to find an appraiser who will agree to share their experience in determining a reasonable value, but, as a rule, monetary appraisals are confidential in nature, and independent appraisers working in the market are reluctant to share their pricing methods. Experts should distinguish between the indicative price, the starting price and the actual sale price, taking into account the impact of the commission in the case of an auction sale and the “hammer price”.

The monetary appraisal of archival donations was initiated in the early 1970s by a committee of the Canadian Historical Association, consisting of three historians and two archivists. The legal and fiscal aspects of donations in kind, practical methods for determining their market value, and the creation of a fair appraisal system to avoid questionable practices were considered by the National Archives of Canada in 1970 at the conference "Donors, Taxmen and Archivists," the materials of which are available on the Internet.

Information on the formation of policies for the acquisition of archives and collections, the development of appraisal tools, and the preparation of archival fonds for monetary appraisal can be obtained from published manuals and methodological developments. A series of such practical guides has been published by the National Library and Archives of Quebec, which contain standards and guidelines for the management of parliamentary fonds and consider the possibilities for their transfer, analyses the nature and purpose of the archives of architectural firms, political parties, business archives, personal and family archives, and explains the procedures to be followed with donors.

Auction catalogues used by Canadian experts – both printed and online – and auction sites such as eBay, American Book Exchange, and Lewis Fine Art Auctions are valuable sources for research. Some auctions publish pre-sale catalogues with starting prices and often add supplements after sales with actual prices achieved.

Individual elements of the monetary appraisal of manuscripts and the procedures used to determine “fair market value” are explored in David Walden's early 1980s publication “Stretching the Dollar: Monetary Appraisal of Manuscripts” (Walden, 1980–1981). The author analyses the differences in the views of archivists and dealers in determining the monetary value of manuscripts, questions the usefulness of the concept of fair market price, and points to the need for close cooperation between archivists and those responsible for appraising

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documents. D. Walden called on archivists to monitor monetary appraisal processes in order to avoid discrepancies between fair market value and research value.

Information on the monetary appraisal of audiovisual documents can be found in Sam Kula's book "Appraising Moving Images: Assessing the Archival and Monetary Value of Film and Video Records" (Kula, 2002) and Brock Silversides' "Preparing For Monetary Appraisals" (Silversides, 2004). Kula's book was the first fundamental work devoted to the archival and monetary appraisal of audiovisual documents, setting out the techniques, methodology and criteria for the monetary appraisal of moving images. The author's explanations of the characteristics of audiovisual documents as objects of appraisal, the concept of comparative pricing, factors influencing the value of audiovisual documents, and the complexity of appraisal criteria are of source-study significance for covering this topic.

The information on the CCEEBC website is valuable in view of this institution's policy on the certification of cultural artefacts. The website categorises cultural values as objects of art, history, science (archaeology, minerals, ethnography, applied and decorative arts, science and technology, musical arts, audiovisual collections – film, video, new media) and characterises the criteria for classifying documents as part of the national cultural heritage. Of interest to our research are the policies, standards, procedures and methods for determining fair market value developed by the CCEEBC (Headings: "Certification of cultural property" ("Attestation de biens culturels"), "Examination of an export licence application" ("Examen d'une demande de licence d'exportation"), "Resources" ("Ressources"). The materials on the website reveal the role and contribution of the CCEEBC in developing methodological and regulatory principles for the examination and monetary appraisal of archival documents.

A number of websites recommended by Canadian experts as benchmarks for determining the value of archival documents contain selling prices for archival documents. The websites reflect a range of associations, societies, and auctions that have addressed the issue of monetary appraisal. The sections "manuscripts", "old papers", "historical manuscripts", and "autographs" on the websites of the Antiquarian Booksellers' Association of America (Librairie Le Chercheur de trésors, ArtPrice, Christie's, Sotheby's), the Society for Political Cartooning (Heritage Auctions) (weekly online auction of rare books and autographs) feature manuscripts, photographs, cartographic documents, diaries and other types of documents and their selling prices.

Basic conceptual principles of monetary appraisal of archival documents. Let us briefly define the goals and objectives of monetary appraisal in Canada. First and foremost, such appraisal is determined for the purposes of insurance and inheritance settlement (Lebeau, 2013–2014). Monetary appraisal for insurance purposes is carried out in the case of loans for exhibitions or media projects. The monetary value of borrowed archives is increased by the cost of transportation.

The catalyst for solving problems and developing methods for monetary appraisal of archives was the decision by state authorities to grant tax breaks to individuals and legal entities making charitable donations. For many institutions, donating archives in exchange for tax breaks is the main means of acquiring personal archives. Since the 1960s, the Canadian government has been encouraging donations of cultural assets, including archival documents. Collections were donated to Canadian archives, libraries and non-profit organisations in exchange for tax credits (tax credits ranging from 4% to 33%, depending on provincial regulations). Tax credit rates apply to all donations.

The tax incentive strategy has proven effective in preserving and protecting the country's documentary heritage. Compensation from the Canadian tax system is intended to encourage individuals who own valuable archives to transfer them to institutions and then make them available for research.

Conceptual criteria for monetary appraisal. Starting in the late 1960s, Canadian researchers developed a hierarchy of criteria for monetary appraisal, laying the foundations for the philosophy underlying the valuation of various types of documents. One of the founders of the CNÉA, archival document dealer and autograph expert R. Gordon, considering appraisal to be a system, developed a monetary appraisal table taking into account the type of documents, their degree of importance and selling prices. The CNÉA appraisal committees, in coordinating the appraisal of archival documents, attempted to formulate criteria that are decisive in monetary appraisal: research value, historical significance, cultural value, exhibition value, origin (a recognised person or the so-called “celebrity effect”), age, rarity, state of preservation, accessibility. Research value implies the constant use of documents by researchers; historical value indicates that the archival collection documents the history of society, community, or family; cultural value reminds us that each work reflects in its own way the civilisation in which it was created.

Canadian scientists see a direct link between research potential and the value of a document. In their opinion, expert evaluators should know whether documents shed new light on a particular historical event, contradict a widely held thesis, or provide an opportunity to interpret the situation differently (Carroll, 2007). According to experts, diaries that illustrate the diversity of life, document aspects of local history that are not found elsewhere, draw attention to details, and are characterised by a long period of entries are of particular research value.

When assessing monetary value, Canadian archivists believe that the criteria for archival value should be taken into account: evidential value (the ability to provide evidence and information about the creation, structure, and functions of the subject), administrative significance (the usefulness and importance of the records to the organisation that created them), legal value (the significance of records for documenting the rights and interests of a person or organisation), historical value, informational value (usefulness and significance regardless of evidentiary, administrative, legal, or historical value), intrinsic value (the significance of a record based on its physical qualities and an integral part of its material nature) (Burant, Brown, Larose, 2022).

The criterion for evaluation is the level of significance of archival documents. Provided that documentary monuments are of regional (provincial) importance, i.e. are important for one region, this will be sufficient to recognise the archival collection as significant on a national scale.

The CCEEBC's certification of national significance of cultural value does not yet establish its market value. The latter will depend on the potential of the collection and the nature of sales on the market, the presence or absence of autographs and other criteria: origin, uniqueness, availability of information from other sources, completeness, age, reliability, authenticity, scientific interest, personality of the creator or donor (Carroll, 2007).

When justifying the value of documents, appraisers must describe their state of preservation. The unsatisfactory condition of a document (trimmed margins, holes, traces of mould or moisture, fragility and breakage, damage caused by insects or rodents, fading and illegibility, ink stains) affects its price (Kennedy, 2007). If documents require restoration work, their price will be reduced.

The set of evaluation criteria proposed by P. Kennedy: aesthetic and physical characteristics (beautiful works in perfect condition attract collectors, but archivists should give preference to content over aesthetics); cultural factors (symbols, emblems, languages, customs, life stories of women, children or minorities); connection with famous people or constitutional, political, military, religious, economic, social or scientific events; exceptional nature or rarity (unique in its category); author's competence, point of view (participant or observer); level of language, testimony of children, women, aborigines or representatives of minorities; number of documents and completeness of the collection; evidence accompanying the documents – processes

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of creation and preservation, places of preservation and areas of activity; presence of special elements: seals, bindings, presentation boxes, etc. (may indicate that the author of the document attached importance, prestige or value to it as an exhibition object); the cost of copyright (the cost of patents for inventions or trade secrets) (Kennedy, 2007).

Mireille Lebeau, archivist at the National Library and Archives of Quebec in Montreal, describes the criteria that must be taken into account to establish fair market value: rarity, complementarity, age, originality, and uniqueness. These attributes determine the exceptional nature of a document. A document that is unique in its category may be a patent, a manuscript of an unpublished work, an interview (audio or film) with indigenous peoples or individuals who have witnessed a well-known or significant event that is poorly documented. Other criteria should also be taken into account: authenticity, collectible value and prestige (e.g. an autographed photograph), combined with rarity and originality; historical value (related to a place, event or person, for example: photographs, letters, recordings of prominent figures, manuscripts of works by writers of national or international renown); exhibition value; level of significance (local, regional, national); state of preservation; scientific and research value. For many appraisers, research value is one of the most important criteria in determining monetary value, prevailing over age and rarity. (Lebeau, 2013–2014).

M. Lebeau, like other researchers – Jim Burant and Marcel Caya – pointed to such a criterion as sentimental value, i.e. the value determined by the donor, which characterises his or her connection with the archive he or she disposes of. However, sentimental value is rarely realised at the level of monetary value. Therefore, an archival institution that acquires private collections of archival documents does not in any way link sentimental value to archival donations (Caya, 1995).

The monetary appraisal of different categories of archival fonds is based on certain criteria, both general and specific. Guy Diné, Assistant Secretary General and Head of the Archives Department at Laval University, has defined the following criteria for political archives (listed by the author in no particular order of importance): research value, age of documents, rarity, complementarity, representativeness (region, party, function), integrity of the collection, state of preservation, originality of the documents, influence of the creator of the collection, market for the collection or specific items, restrictions on access and reproduction, format or medium of the documents, and existing laws regarding the public or private status of the documents (Guy, 2007). Not all political archives are of equal historical importance, so it is difficult to develop a uniform approach to their evaluation. For example, a small collection of a political organiser, lawyer, and first French-speaking leader of the Canadian government, Wilfrid Laurier, from the 19th and early 20th centuries, consisting of original letters with autographs of politicians, will not be evaluated in the same way as a large collection (over 50 linear metres) of a parliamentarian from the 1980s on his relations with the citizens of his constituency (Guy, 2007). That is why, as experts have pointed out, the following elements need to be taken into account in the appraisal process: determining the potential market for the collection or its individual parts, grouping documents by class depending on the importance of the basic appraisal units (box, file, separate item), the availability of accompanying documents, establishing an average value for different components of the collection, increasing the price in percentage terms for intact collections, reducing the value in percentage terms due to access restrictions, comparing the valuation amount with similar collections that have been valued in recent years. The statistics on the monetary appraisal of the collections of political parties, political organisers and parliamentarians presented in the works reflect the methodology and results of the appraisal (Guy, 2007) and show that the appraisal is not based on predetermined rules. Depending on the period, the content of the archival fonds or collections, and the functions performed by their creator, appraisers adapt their methodology and

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take into account the weight of each of the criteria that influence the monetary appraisal. This is especially true for contemporary political archives, where the real market value and the importance of the documents for future research must be taken into account.

An important criterion in evaluating collections is their integrity. The Hudson's Bay Company (Compagnie de la Baie d'Hudson) archive, according to auctioneer David Silcox, was valued at 20% more “because the whole collection is worth more than the sum of its parts” (Silcox, 2007). A complete collection is always more valuable. Archives do not want to receive a donation of a collection from which the best works have been removed, leaving only press releases and clippings. Donors of archival collections often believe that fragmenting and transferring them in stages will result in a higher valuation. However, segmenting collections is counterproductive because the value will be higher if they remain intact.

The criteria of completeness and research value are taken into account when evaluating corporate archives. The largest archival collections come from large companies. The Canadian Association of Archivists' brochure “Business Archives” reasonably asked the question, “What are our archives worth and will anyone want to buy them?” (Salmon, 2007). Monetary appraisal requires familiarity with similar documents before calculating the average cost. It is essential to take into account the quantity, nature and types of documents.

Canadian archivists, CNÉA experts and university professors have drawn attention to the criteria for evaluating literary archives, based on their experience of work with collections of French-language writers. The monetary value of literary heritage is influenced by the aura surrounding writers, the publicity hype following the publication of their works, their presence in the media and show business, the research potential of literary collections, and the work of literary scholars and critics with writers' legacies. Manuscripts, diaries, correspondence of Canada's most famous writers, and their early works are highly valued by collectors, scholars, and scientists. The monetary value of letters may depend on their content and their senders or recipients. Researchers cited the example of a literary collection containing 14 letters from Eric Arthur Blair, better known as George Orwell. In the 1980s, these letters were sold for \$10,000 each. It is these aspects that should attract the attention of expert appraisers. (Ostiguy, Brandak, Moldenhauer & Jones, 2007).

One criterion is the collectible value of archival documents. For example, 19th-century letters with high collectible value can cost thousands of dollars if sold separately. Other letters derive their value from being part of a complete collection. Some may have research value but little market value on their own (Elwood, 2007).

When evaluating digital archival documents, Canadian experts consider the following criteria: authenticity; relevance; condition; volume; archival, research, historical and cultural value. With regard to authenticity, it is important to determine whether the digital versions correspond to the description. It is also worth checking the original source, as digital documents are easy to copy and reproduce (duplication is common in digital collections, which affects the value of the collection), assessing whether the digital versions have been altered, checking the metadata of the documents to ensure there are no losses, and investigating the relevance of the records, i.e. how well they correspond to the functions and powers of the institutions (Lunsford & Mobbs, 2007).

Conclusions

Sources of information on the appraisal of archival artefacts in Canada are quite representative and provide an overview of the history of the organisation of these processes and the results of their implementation. Despite differences in the objectives and organisation of the appraisal process, the conceptual approaches to the process itself in Canada and Ukraine are almost

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identical. This is indicated by the content of the criteria described in the sources of information on the appraisal of archival documents in Canada and the domestic Methodology for the Monetary Appraisal of Documents of the National Archival Fonds (*Metodyka Hroshovoi Otsinky*, 2005). The criteria for evaluating archival documents (level of significance, collection value, presence of rare illustrations and decorations, state of preservation, etc.) can be extrapolated to the practice of libraries purchasing rare and unique library collections and individual publications. The experience of Canadian archivists is valuable and requires in-depth study, especially in the areas of monetary appraisal of audiovisual documents and documents in electronic form.

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Досвід Канади щодо грошової оцінки архівних документів: характеристика джерел дослідження та основні концепції

Мета – окреслення основних джерел інформації щодо грошового оцінювання архівних документів та аналіз основних концептуальних засад здійснення цього процесу. **Методика.** Під час виконання завдань дослідження було застосовано методи: історико-джерелознавчий, історико-порівняльний, поняттєвого аналізу. **Результати.** Охарактеризовано основні джерела інформації щодо оцінювання архівних документів, зокрема сайти Національної ради з оцінки архівів, Бібліотеки та архіву Канади, Канадської комісії з контролю за експортом культурних цінностей, Асоціації продавців антикварних книг Америки, матеріали конференції в Оттаві 2007 р. «Майбутнє грошової оцінки в Канаді», доповіді форуму (2022 р.), присвячених темі «Набагато більше ніж гроші». Визначено основні концептуальні засади, що застосовують під час визначення грошової оцінки документів архівісти та інші експерти. **Висновки.** Джерела інформації щодо оцінювання архівних артефактів у Канаді цілком репрезентативні та надають загальну картину організації цих процесів і результатів їх здійснення. Визначені критерії оцінки архівних документів цілком можуть бути застосовані під

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час оцінювання й купівлі бібліотечних колекцій та окремих книжкових пам'яток. Незважаючи на відмінності в організації проведення оцінювання, концептуальні підходи до самого процесу в Канаді та Україні майже подібні. Однак досвід канадських архівістів є цінним і потребує поглибленого вивчення, особливо в напрямках грошового оцінювання аудіовізуальних документів і документів у електронній формі.

Ключові слова: грошова оцінка; архівні документи; концепції; джерела дослідження; архіви; бібліотеки; Канада

Received: 14.07.2025

Accepted: 12.11.2025